

Research-based Student Selected Components (SSCs)

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Why do a
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What does it
involve?

Is it for
you?

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- To tick off key skills

Key skills:

- a piece of medical writing
- describing a literature search
- giving a presentation
- writing an abstract

A person in a white shirt is sitting at a desk, writing on a notepad with a red pen. The desk is cluttered with various items, including a laptop, a mouse, and several pens. The background is slightly blurred, showing another person's hands and a laptop. The overall scene suggests a professional or academic setting.

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What does a research-based SSC involve?

- Broadly two approaches

**Contributing to an ongoing
piece of research**

Running a research project

What does a research-based SSC involve?

Example tasks when running a research project:

Preparation

- Project planning
- Pre-reading
- Learning objectives

Planning

- Literature review
- Research Plan
- Data Access

Experiments

- Experiments

Dissemination

- Project Report
- Project Presentation
- Conference Submission
- Journal Publication

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Is a research-based SSC for you?

Consider:

- Are you interested in the research topic?
- Are you interested in doing research?
- Do you get along with the supervisor?
- Are you willing to work largely independently?
- Are you happy to learn new skills?
- Are you prepared to be proactive and solve problems yourself?
- Would the project meet your expectations?

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Scott Graham,
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For further information:
<https://peterhcharlton.github.io>